

Deliverable 6.4

Sustaining mAKE

Due date of deliverable: 31/01/2025

Actual submission date: 04/02/2025

Start date of project: 01/02/2022 Duration (36 Months)

Dissemination Level: Public ✓

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP6 Community Engagement and Sustainability
Deliverable	D6.4 Sustainability Report
Document Name	D6.4 Sustaining mAKE
Due Date	M36: 31 January 2025
Submission Date	M37: 4 February 2025
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential
Deliverable Lead	Global Innovation Gathering (GIG)
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Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document describes the sustainability plan for the project's legacy past the funding term.
Keywords	Maker Movement, DIHs, Sustainability, Co-creation, Open-Source, Makerspaces.

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the mAKE project consortium under EC grant agreement number 101016858 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
001	25.06.24	Initial structure and outline
002	10.12.24	Main content added to all sections
002.1	13.12.24	Co-creation and content inputs with allocated consortium members
002.2	22.12.24	WP leader inputs
003	28.01.25	Peer review and detailed feedback on overall structure and specific content
004	31.01.25	Integration of peer review comments
1.00	01.02.25	Final editing

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AIOSH	African Institute of Open Science and Hardware
API	Application Programme Interface
APSOHA	Association pour la Promotion de la Science Ouverte en Haïti et en Afrique
AU	African Union
CC	Community Connector
DI	Digital Innovation
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
DITO	Data In, Data Out
DM	distributed manufacturing
DSI	digital social innovation
EBIMS	Engage, Build, Inspire, Maintain and Sustain
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FCF	Fab City Foundation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
GreenTec	GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation
H2020	Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
IAAC	Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
IMA	Innovative Manufacturing in Africa project
IOPA	Internet of Production Alliance
IP	intellectual property
LAUDS	Local Accessible Urban Digital Sustainable Factories project

MEL	monitoring, evaluation, and learning
MiR	Makers-in-Residency
MOOC	massive open online course
Open AIR	Open African Innovation Research network
OCBM	Open Catalogue of Business Models
OERs	open educational resources
OKW	Open Know Where standard
OMT	Open Makerspace Toolkit
PENCE	Power Europe Narrative for Civic Ecology project
PITO	Product In, Trash Out
PSS	People and Skills Specification
RLabs	Reconstructed Living Labs
R&I	Research & Innovation
RISA	Research and Innovation Systems for Africa
SEADE	Strengthening the Europe-Africa Digital Ecosystem Through Increased R&I Cooperation
SMEs	small and medium-sized enterprises
TOT	training-of-trainers
T&W	Technology and Knowledge Unit
UCT	University of Cape Town
WP	work package
WP6	work package 6: Community Engagement and Sustainability
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation

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1. Executive Summary

This document reports on the Sustainability activities that have been developed within the framework of the mAKE project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 101016858.

The mAKE project aimed to create lasting connections between African and European makerspaces. When designing the project legacy, a strategy for sustainability was developed based on the consortium partners embedding all project outputs into their organisational portfolios rather than creating project structures that would not be sustained after the project's end. This sustainability report illustrates the project's dedication to promoting innovation, ensuring financial sustainability, and fostering environmental stewardship.

Key Approaches

1. **Co-Creation Activities:** Involving both consortium members and external communities in the co-creation of knowledge products, so as to encourage acceptance and promote the effective use of the project's outcomes.
2. **Embedding Strategies:** Promoting ongoing collaboration and resource-sharing while integrating practices among consortium members and associated partners.
3. **Qualitative Interviews:** Through in-depth discussions with other Horizon 2020 projects, gathering best practices and insights that allow mAKE to refine its strategies and maximise its impact. These exchanges have fostered a collaborative spirit, proving essential to the project's adaptable approach.
4. **Open Licensing and Educational Resources:** By sharing outputs under open licences and presenting them as open educational resources (OERs), the project facilitates, and advocates for, accessibility and continued learning.
5. **Sustainability in-Action:** Emphasising sustainability throughout the project and securing funding for related initiatives.
6. **mAKE Legacy:** Establishing a secretariat and a dedicated steering committee composed of consortium members to support ongoing efforts.

Ongoing Initiatives and Sustainability

To ensure the lasting success and relevance of the mAKE project, ongoing initiatives focus on:

- **Establishment of a Secretariat:** A secretariat will be established in Cape Town in 2025 to enhance collaboration within the African Makerspaces community network. This office will concentrate on effective marketing and promotional strategies to raise the visibility and growth of the mAKE legacy across Africa and Europe.
- **Local Outreach and Fundraising:** A dedicated team will spearhead outreach and fundraising initiatives, which are essential for maintaining the project's momentum

and expanding its reach, thereby advancing the objectives of mAKE and its consortium members.

The sustainability strategy's approaches are firmly rooted in community engagement and strategic partnerships, ensuring that mAKE's impact will extend well beyond the initial three-year funding period and create a significant legacy in the African and European makerspace ecosystem alongside the ambition to extend further to the broader global makerspace ecosystems.

2. Introduction

This document details the activities and results to create and implement the Sustainability strategy of the mAKE project and was written at the end of the initial EU funded project duration of three years.

mAKE is focusing on hardware-focused Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), hereinafter called makerspaces, as key drivers for local digital innovation in Africa and Europe. mAKE seeks to grow the sustainability of, and collaborations between, African and European makerspaces and the start-ups they host. The mAKE consortium members engaged in co-creation, knowledge-sharing and capacity development throughout the project, ensuring that all consortium members and their respective networks leave the project's initial funding period with new skills, networks, and capacity to continue working on connecting makerspaces/DIHs in Europe and Africa.

Further, the various mAKE work packages generated outputs, as highlighted herein, that serve as valuable resources for maker communities and ongoing related initiatives, particularly the project's educational toolkits, the mAKE MOOC, training programmes, and the Map of Machinery. These resources are not only available via the mAKE website but also as white-label products that can be used by others, further developed, and integrated into mAKE consortium members' portfolios—thereby enabling the exploitation of project results after the project's initial funding period ends. The following chapters serve as an overview of mAKE's co-creation and embedding activities, they highlight outputs up to this point and provide insights to contributions from all partners to sustain mAKE in the future.

3. Co-Creation Activities

The mAKE Co-Creation Report (D6.2)¹ highlights that, within the mAKE framework, co-creation entails collaborative approaches to achieving project objectives. Adopting a multi-stakeholder strategy during the project's design and development proved to be essential. As the project evolved, the Community Engagement and Sustainability (WP6) team conducted one in-person workshop during the first half of 2024 and a follow-up workshop in November 2024, both centred on sustainability planning for the mAKE legacy

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14442691>

beyond the initial funding period. Additionally, three comprehensive online co-creation sessions were convened from July to October 2024, using Jamboard² to collect inputs.

Figure 1. Screenshots of the co-creation session online whiteboards

These workshops and online sessions encouraged open discussions and creative brainstorming, enabling participants to explore innovative solutions and identify potential obstacles. This strategy bolstered the consortium's internal unity and commitment to the project's continuation, and strengthened ties with external partners, ensuring that the project's outcomes will remain relevant and adaptable to evolving circumstances.

Figure 2. Screenshot of a presentation on sustainability during the ICT-58 family meeting

To further enrich the project through co-creation, mAKE representatives joined the H2020 ICT-58 family's monthly calls³ during the project's duration, including calls dedicated to the aligned projects' sustainability planning. These collaborative interactions within the H2020 ICT-58 family have enhanced mAKE's sustainability strategies through more diversified perspectives and observations and cultivated a sense of community and collective purpose between mAKE and like-minded initiatives. Through the discussions we found that the post-runtime sustainability project and self-sustainable ecosystem could be the unanimous consensus on sustainability strategies for different projects. Integrating insights

² [Google Jamboard: Whiteboard App for Business | Google Workspace](#) (a discontinued service by the time of submission of this report)

³ [Meeting with our ICT-58 Family projects page 2 - AfriConEU](#)

from ICT-58 family projects has expanded mAKE’s scope, through incorporation of lessons learnt and best practices from these parallel initiatives.

In addition to the monthly calls and informal discussions, mAKE interviewed three other H2020 ICT-58 family projects, *DIGILOGIC*, *HUBiqitous* and *ENRICH in Africa*, so that the learnings could be summarized in this report and other interested parties can incorporate the sustainability insights and reflections into future sustainability strategies. The team found this especially valuable as it is not often possible to get access to such reflections after the initial project funding ended. *(Please find the summaries of the interviews in Appendix B of this document.)*

In July 2024, mAKE’s communication team hosted a summer training for the mAKE community focused on co-creation towards “mapping the customer journey”. In business terms, the customer journey is a series of steps, starting with a person’s awareness of a brand even before becoming a customer of the services behind the brand. The journey eventually leads to a “purchase” (or, in a non-commercial endeavour such as mAKE, use of services), and eventual customer loyalty⁴. In the mAKE context, the customer journey represents the path of the stakeholders that mAKE targets through the platform/s where mAKE outputs are embedded. This path can be divided into three levels:

- **Macro-level:** Customer 1: e.g., international development cooperation representative
- **Meso-level:** Customer 2: e.g., Afrilabs Community Lead
- **Micro-level:** Customer 3: e.g., an individual maker

Figure 3: Visual representation to introduce the co-creation session on mapping the customer journey

⁴ <https://business.adobe.com/blog/basics/customer-journey>

Comparing insights from the customer journey mapping to those of the co-creation sessions brought out the critical need for an integrated, inclusive, and user-centred platform to meet all kinds of needs in this mAKE ecosystem. This has been a core consideration in the consortium members' plans for sustaining the project resources within their respective portfolios.

As the mAKE project advances, it remains dedicated to fostering collaborative networks and continuing its co-creation journey. By cultivating shared learning, the project aspires to leave a lasting legacy that champions the maker movement's transformative potential.

4. Embedding Strategies: An Overview of Sustained Outputs and Activities

The mAKE Community Activation and Engagement Strategy (D6.1)⁵ identifies a spectrum of seven circles (or orbits) of networks. The “mAKErverse” is the umbrella term or ecosystem in which this spectrum engages communities—from the individual level through to the city, country, region, continental and global levels—to amplify the value and impact of makerspaces and makers.

Figure 4. Seven orbits of networks in the “mAKErverse”

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/7635676>

During the project's initial three-year funding period, new collaborations were enabled across European and African networks of DIHs. The project formed strong alliances across all seven identified levels within the "mAkErverse", and key highlights were on the continental networks level (level O5) of the mAkErverse (Figure 4.):

- A closer partnership with Vulca, the network of 42 European makerspaces, which e.g. was instrumental to ensure more active participation in the MiR call for applications from Europe.
- A strengthened connection with R Labs, which is a community network active in Africa with 24 country offices, including planning the mAkE legacy together whereby a secretariat will be established and continue to promote the mAkE project at the official R Labs headquarters in Cape Town.
- A strengthened connection to the Afrilabs network, which has supported DIHs across African countries since 2011. The collaboration culminated in the inclusion of an official makerspace programme track for the first time in the 9th annual Afrilabs pan-African event, in 2024 hosted in South Africa.

Figure 5. Co-design for communities to share and embed resources

Further, the mAkE consortium members themselves have also formulated their ambition and roles in the cultivation and exploitation of the mAkE deliverables after the initial project period. In this way, mAkE will, going forward, continue to involve a broad range of

stakeholders from across Africa and Europe to increase awareness, interest and continued engagement and ownership for mAKE, as follows:

GreenTec

GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation (GreenTec) is the non-profit arm of the GreenTec group. GreenTec's focus lies on promoting investment in African entrepreneurship. For investors, GreenTec provides guidance and access to the African entrepreneurship scene; for entrepreneurs, GreenTec offers expert advice and matchmaking. GreenTec fosters the entire ecosystem by creating knowledge, bringing stakeholders together, and putting African entrepreneurship in the limelight. GreenTec's contributions to continuation of mAKE will include:

- **Inclusion of Makerspace Visits During Investor Trips:** To create visibility for makerspaces and enable investors better to understand their concept, impact, and potential. These visits also facilitate engagement with the makerspace community, a vital component of their ecosystem.
- **Reflection on Social Entrepreneurship and Founder Diversity:** Building on insights from the Train-the-Trainers (ToT) programme for the mAKE Venture Building Handbook, future venture building and training sessions will place greater emphasis on social entrepreneurship and the diverse perspectives, ambitions, and personalities of founders. This approach acknowledges the varied motivations and viewpoints within the entrepreneurial landscape.
- The **Venture Building Handbook** has proven to be an invaluable resource for startups, SMEs, and makerspaces, and thus it will continue to be used, and further developed, for the benefit of ventures in Africa and Europe.

Fab City Foundation

The **Fab City Foundation** (FCF) champions its Global Initiative through pioneering projects in social innovation, urban research, and educational programmes. The Foundation fosters a network of forward-thinking cities, organises the annual Fab City Summit with local partners, and leads strategic research on transformative urban models such as the Fab City Full Stack and the "Product In, Trash Out" (PITO) to "Data In, Data Out" (DIDO) transition.

The Fab City Global Initiative has supported the mAKE in developing three key deliverables:

- A **comprehensive report**⁶ documenting national and regional hub associations, featuring seven detailed case studies and comparative analysis.
- The **Common Policy Agenda**⁷, which outlines shared policy priorities and recommendations

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/7759420>

⁷ <https://makeafricaeu.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/CPA-June-2024.pdf>

- The "**Minister Meet Maker**" **Dialogues Report**⁸, capturing insights from discussions between policy makers and makers.

The Fab City Foundation commits to furthering the legacy of mAKE in the following ways:

- The Common Policy Agenda will serve as a valuable resource for connecting makerspace communities to the Fab City Network while also creating opportunities to onboard African cities into the network through makerspaces.
- The Common Policy Agenda, the report on the seven National case studies, the "Minister Meets Maker" Dialogue Report, and other resources from mAKE will be hosted in the Fab City Open Resources Library. These materials will be accessible to the broader Fab City community and support city administrations and councils in implementing strategies for local production.
- The Fab City Foundation will host two Policy Lab sessions at the Fab City Summit in the Czech Republic in July 2025 as part of the Power Europe Narrative for Civic Ecology project (PENCE). These sessions will be framed using insights from the mAKE policy research and stakeholder engagements.

APSOHA

The **Association pour la Promotion de la Science Ouverte en Haïti et en Afrique** (APSOHA) is a non-religious, non-political, and non-profit organisation that aims to democratise digital manufacturing, promote citizen science, combat cognitive injustice, and provide open educational resources (OERs). Since its creation in Yaoundé, Cameroon, in 2016, APSOHA has engaged in numerous collaborative and knowledge-exchange activities with its members and partners.

- In mAKE WP3, its primary deliverable has been the **mAKE MOOC**⁹, a shared online platform hosting both existing and newly created open-source training content from the mAKE initiative. This platform also includes cross-cutting training modules on equity, inclusion of vulnerable groups, women engineers, youth employment, and diversity.
- After the project initial funding period, the mAKE MOOC will continue its operations. Its sustainability will be guaranteed by the **African Institute of Open Science and Hardware (AIOSH)**¹⁰, a branch of APSOHA devoted to formal education in free and open source hardware. Established in 2023, AIOSH is set to commence its activities in 2025. AIOSH will undertake the following responsibilities:
 - ◆ Maintaining the MOOC platform to ensure its long-term functionality.

⁸ <https://makeafricaeu.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Minister-meet-Maker-Dialogues-Report-2024.pdf>

⁹ <https://makeafricaeu.moodlecloud.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ahiosh.org/>

- ◆ Ensuring that the platform and all its courses are accessible, enabling innovators, hub promoters, and the general public to benefit from lifelong learning opportunities.
- ◆ Collaborating with additional makerspace/DIH projects, offering those interested the option to host their courses on the platform.
- ◆ Ensuring that all content on the platform is openly licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) licence, allowing it to be used, reused, and built upon by others.
- ◆ Addressing language barriers, with content translated into either French or English, as appropriate.

Internet of Production Alliance

The **Internet of Production Alliance** (IOPA) is a global network reimagining the future—united in a common goal to revolutionise the way we source, manufacture and deliver products. It is building open infrastructures that enable anyone, everywhere, to participate in production through distributed manufacturing (DM).

Its primary focus areas are:

- Open standards and protocols—Maintaining the open standards and protocols necessary for an internet of production that supports decentralised supply networks.
- Practical & accessible knowledge—Gather and sharing information on how DM can work in practice to inform its work on standards and pave the way for a future of decentralised production.

The IOPA believes that the future of production lies in decentralised manufacturing based on shared knowledge. This would allow producers to deliver products faster, made from locally sourced materials, and with less ecological impact.

As the lead of WP4: Distributed Manufacturing Network during mAKE's initial funding period, the IOPA has developed:

- The Mutual Recognition of Skills Standard (PSS¹¹), which creates a framework for the development of Maker Passports, enabling makers to showcase their skills and making it easier for them to be contacted for DM opportunities or business collaborations.
- The Map of Machinery¹², based on the Open Know Where (OKW¹³) standard, which can be used:
 - ◆ to locate facilities suitable to manufacture designs;
 - ◆ to leverage local DM and create jobs;

¹¹ [People and Skills Specification](#)

¹² <https://map.internetofproduction.org/makeafricaeu.html>

¹³ <https://www.internetofproduction.org/openknowwhere>

- ◆ to provide makerspaces with access to, and guidelines for, best practices and resources; and
 - ◆ to enable organisations to quickly identify and procure critical supplies in emergency response.
- A contracting system prototype¹⁴ for DM, allowing buyers to manage orders across multiple manufacturers using a single interface, and automating workflows to ensure clarity and accountability for everyone involved.

All technical specifications, recommendations and use cases of these innovations are shared under open licences on Zenodo, PubPub, GitHub, OpenStreetMap, and ActivePieces, as well as on the Internet of Production Community Forum¹⁵.

All innovations are developed to be self-sustaining:

- Based on the Open Standard of Mutual Recognition of Skills (PSS), makerspaces can develop their own system to create maker passports. Continuing the work on the maker passport, a Maker Passport platform¹⁶ prototype has been developed by IOPA as part of the Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project 2024, funded by the Research and Innovation Systems for Africa (RISA) Fund and the UK government. This platform is designed to help makers showcase their profiles, skills, certifications (with issuance details and digital badges), location, and links to personal or professional websites, social media accounts, and projects. The aim is to connect makers with potential collaborators or clients based on their skills, certifications, and location.
- The Map of Machinery can be adopted and adapted. All information for data collection, data assessment and design is available on GitHub¹⁷. The self-submission form enables makerspaces to update their profiles.
- The source code and the workflows of the DM contracting system prototype are available on GitHub for others to utilise.
- All technical innovations and specifications have been added to Wikipedia¹⁸ for more extensive access.

The IOPA will ensure the maintenance of all infrastructures developed. The work will continue with the community on the maker passports, the map of machinery and the contracting system to support makerspaces and distributed contracting globally.

¹⁴ <https://distributed-orders.fly.dev/>

¹⁵ <https://community.internetofproduction.org/>

¹⁶ <https://maker-passport.fly.dev/about>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/>

¹⁸ e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distributed_manufacturing

Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC

Fab Lab Barcelona was one of the first Fab Labs funded in the European Union (founded in 2007) and is now a benchmark in a robust network of over 1,800 Fab Labs in over 100 countries. It produces world-leading research and innovation at its e digital fabrication laboratory. Based at the **Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)**, Fab Lab Barcelona uses its digital fabrication facilities to prototype, fabricate and test ideas in the real world as research, education and innovation activities.

Fab Lab Barcelona, with the support of IAAC, will undertake the following in support of mAKE's mission beyond the initial funding period:

- Fab Lab Barcelona commits to referencing and showcasing the mAKE project and its outcomes on its website, newsletters, and connected social media accounts. This will amplify the project's outreach and continue fostering a network for sharing best practices.
- Essential resources and learning materials (e.g., the MOOC) developed during the mAKE project will be shared through one of Fab Lab Barcelona's long-term research initiatives and network leads, the Distributed Design Platform¹⁹. The Distributed Design Platform promotes and supports emerging creative talents working at the intersection of design, innovation, and making practices. Since 2017, it has been funded by Creative Europe and, in 2024, launched a [Learning Hub](#)²⁰ that serves as a cornerstone for making learning materials accessible to a global community of changemakers. The Platform and its Learning Hub are integral components of Fab Lab Barcelona, backed by a long-term sustainability plan, making them an ideal cornerstone for continuing the legacy of mAKE.
- Communication and branding materials developed within the mAKE framework will be made available for reuse and repurposing by African and European Makerspaces for future initiatives. All branding materials will be shared under the Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 licence (CC BY 4.0), allowing commercial and non-commercial reuse, remixing, and sharing with proper attribution to the original authors designers.
- Fab Lab Barcelona further commits to screening EU funding opportunities and co-authoring strategic proposals to ensure the mAKE project's ideas, established networks, and impactful outcomes receive continued support and funding.

GIG

The **Global Innovation Gathering (GIG)** is a global network connecting DIHs and other grassroots initiatives in all continents, including Europe and Africa. As a membership organisation, it creates research and innovation initiatives, outreach events and provides peer-knowledge exchange and support for its more than 200 members around the world

¹⁹ <https://distributeddesign.eu/>

²⁰ <https://learn.distributeddesign.eu/>

that contribute to sustainable development. GIG led the community engagement and sustainability and contributed to all WPs. Some highlights of the activities, further outlined in the Final Impact Assessment Report (D7.3), are as follows:

- More than 400 community members engaged through a total of 13 dedicated community calls and webinars hosted by GIG during 2024/2025.
- Mutual learning and experience-sharing, between the mAKE consortium and the project's stakeholders was facilitated through the implementation of two series of online events, the "Knowledge Pills" (9 videos) and the "mAKE talks" (7 videos).
- Due to mAKE project activities, 30 new individuals and 15 makerspaces/organisations joined the GIG community and were on-boarded in GIG's communication channels, gaining access to numerous opportunities and valuable resources. This integration has allowed these new community members to connect with counterparts worldwide, fostering an exchange of best practices within the ecosystem.
- The mAKE community was showcased at a dedicated makerspace at the annual re:publica²¹ conference with 10.000 participants in Berlin, Germany annually from 2022 - 2024. The event provided an annual opportunity to share impact stories, provide training and workshops and connect EU and AU makers together.
- In support of mAKE's Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), GIG hosted community discussion webinars, with a focus on community inputs for, awareness of, and engagement with, the OCBM.
- wrote several funding proposals to small and big public and private funds together with mAKE community members, to enable global uptake of project results and support activities of community members e.g. to Creative Europe, Horizon Europe, CISCO foundation, Stiftung Nord-Süd-Brücken, Robert Bosch Foundation, Volkswagen Foundation etc.
- In order to share recommendations gained through the mAKE project as well as critical lessons learnt through the MIR programme, GIG developed the "'Right to Repair Policy Directive' and the 'Policy Brief: Improving Visa Policies for African Innovators in International Cooperation Projects,' which will be shared on both the GIG website and the mAKE project website (see Appendix C and D).

As part of GIGs dedication to the legacy of the mAKE project, the organisation endeavours to support the ongoing community engagement and embedding and sharing of resources through the following;

- The mAKE community will continue to be engaged through GIG Community Calls which take place on a monthly basis
 - ◆ Additionally, members are invited to showcase their work across all GIG channels, increasing their visibility and public recognition.

²¹ <https://www.re-publica.com/en>

- GIG will feature mAKE results and the mAKE community at in-person events throughout the next years, highlights will include the prestigious re:publica conference in Berlin where GIG is hosting the pop-up makerspace and the annual Fab Foundation conference²² which is coming to Prague in 2025.
- The online platform created with mAKE is linked to the GIG website, and the GIG community will participate in maintaining it and sharing its content.
 - ◆ One example is embedding the Map of Machinery, which is already shared across the GIG and IOPA websites, hosted as the Social Innovation Atlas²³ on the GIG website.
 - ◆ GIG will continue to share the OCBM through adding the white-labelled version to its website in 2025 and facilitate further community events around business models for DIHs.
- GIG will additionally ensure the mAKE MOOC's long-term relevance and impact, supporting continuous innovation and development across regions.
 - ◆ In this capacity, the platform is already hosting courses from another project piloted by the IOPA, one of mAKE's consortium members. In addition, the Local Accessible Urban Digital Sustainable Factories (LAUDS) project, co-funded by the European Union, is considering using the mAKE MOOC for training purposes.
 - ◆ GIG will build out the community course throughout 2025 in order to add more content which is relevant and meets the needs of the community.
- The first residency programme which hosted 5 African makers and engaged with 5 European makers/makerspaces, was a highlight of the project. The strengthened relationship between the Vulca network²⁴ and GIG has led to further discussion and plans to host more residencies in the future.
- GIG has ensured that the activities are embedded in the mAKE project structure and will continue beyond the duration of the project through assigning a dedicated mAKE project coordinator who will continue to promote the project. Alongside this investment, GIG is actively fundraising to support a makerspace establishment with Rlabs in South Africa as well as fundraising for continued support of mAKE with partners in Europe and globally.

UCT-Open AIR

The **Open African Innovation Research** (Open AIR) is a multidisciplinary network of researchers in over 20 African countries, Canada, and beyond. Open AIR engages stakeholders and mobilises knowledge on practical and policy-legal-regulatory dimensions of open collaborative innovation, innovation scaling, inclusive innovation, and knowledge governance that supports innovation. Open AIR has six hub institutions—in Cairo, Lagos/Abuja, Nairobi, Cape Town, Johannesburg and Ottawa—and connects roughly 150

²² <https://fab25.fabevent.org/>

²³ <https://globalinnovationgathering.org/atlas/>

²⁴ <https://vulca.eu/action/>

experts across disciplines and continents. The network has a presence in Anglophone, Francophone and Lusophone Africa. Open AIR's participation in mAKE is driven by the Open AIR hub at the **University of Cape Town (UCT)**, precisely two entities in the UCT Faculty of Law: the Intellectual Property Unit and the Intaka Centre For Law and Technology.

The findings of Open AIR studies are used to develop working papers, policy briefs, research publications (including journal articles, books and book chapters), and improved theoretical models. Open AIR research publications on African makerspaces include the following:

- Armstrong, C., & Kraemer-Mbula, E. (2022). [Value creation and socioeconomic inclusion in South African maker communities.](#)²⁵
- Armstrong, C., De Beer, J., Kraemer-Mbula, E., & Ellis, M. (2018). [Institutionalisation and informal innovation in South African maker communities.](#)²⁶
- De Beer, J., Armstrong, C., Ellis, M., & Kraemer-Mbula, E. (2017). [A scan of South Africa's maker movement.](#)²⁷

Open AIR sees the makerspaces and other hardware-focused DIHs participating in the mAKE community as key engines for open collaborative innovation and enterprise development in Africa. In support of mAKE's ongoing sustainability beyond the initial funding period, Open AIR, with the support of UCT, will:

- continue to research, and publish findings on, the work of African makerspaces, particularly maker communities active in the activities of mAKE and its consortium members, and
- continue to disseminate mAKE outputs via its website and social media. Examples of mAKE resources currently featured on the [Open AIR website](#)²⁸ include the mAKE Recommendations for Policymakers and the mAKE Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM).

Centre for Social Innovation - ZSI

The **Zentrum für Soziale Innovation** (Centre for Social Innovation) is a transdisciplinary social science research institute. Its Technology and Knowledge Unit (T&W) focuses its research and development activities on the potential and limitations of emerging technologies and their diffusion in technologically mediated settings for the benefit of society. A core activity of T&W is the impact evaluation of socio-technical projects and their interactions with social innovations. Since 2011, T&W researchers have also been involved in studying and implementing citizen science activities; and since 2017 they have studied and promoted the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle in several bioeconomy projects. Additionally, T&W has engaged for many years in maker projects, fostering hands-on, participatory innovation processes and exploring the potential of collaborative production and prototyping for societal benefit.

²⁵ <https://ajic.wits.ac.za/article/view/14245>

²⁶ http://peerproduction.net/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/jopp_issue12_vol1of3.pdf

²⁷ <https://openair.africa/a-scan-of-south-africas-maker-movement/>

²⁸ <https://openair.africa/>

ZSI was the project coordinator and leader of the evaluation and impact assessment activities in the mAKE project. It gathered various lessons from the impact assessment work with makerspaces that will be applied in future projects. ZSI is currently preparing a scientific publication on the impact of the mAKE project and lessons learned from the evaluation, and it will continue to:

- Screen future EC funding calls to continue working with the inspiring network of African and European makerspaces that ZSI got to know during the mAKE project.
- Work with impact stories or community voices, developed in the mAKE project: an inspirational, easy-to-understand communication tool that demonstrates the benefits of using created resources, learning content, networking opportunities, recommendations etc, in different contexts.
- Work towards understanding and building communities around different “levels” – from the micro over the meso to the macro level and investigating impact metrics along these levels.
- Keep track of the mAKE library on Zenodo²⁹.
- Be part of the mAKE secretariat advisory board to bring a research perspective and enrich the secretariat with experiences and links to European funding programmes.

Additional Contributor: Manufacturing Change

Manufacturing Change Ltd. is an organisation that studies today’s dominant production model and emerging alternatives. It analyses supply chains, codifies business models, and builds economic models to make it easier for anyone from an individual entrepreneur to a government or an aid agency to make local manufacturing work for them. Manufacturing Change engages in advocacy work to advance the decentralised manufacturing ecosystem. Going forward:

- Although not a consortium partner, UK-based Manufacturing Change has undertaken to host the LocalEconomies.org³⁰ website and initiative on an ongoing basis. This ensures that the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM) developed under the mAKE project will be further developed, expanded in scope, and promoted.
- Work will continue to deepen the OCBM’s applicability in the open hardware sector and to promote its use in relevant communities.

5. The mAKE legacy: Sustainability-in-Action

The project placed a strong emphasis on implementing sustainability plans at its inception, and this continued in its second and third years. Consequently, this chapter showcases essential activities that enhanced the project’s impact and paved the way for future projects, future funding, and complementary initiatives.

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/make>

³⁰ <http://LocalEconomies.org>

Notably, several initiatives have already become synonymous with the continuation and legacy of mAkE. Some highlights include:

- IOPA secured matching funding to support the OCBM from the Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project. This funding facilitated the development of a dedicated website³¹ and its translation into French in late 2023. The IMA³² is funded by the UK International Development's Research and Innovation Systems for Africa (RISA) Fund³³.
- Additional funding was allocated for makerspaces in Africa through consortium member IOPA and the RISA Fund in 2024, which has helped connect and promote makerspaces on the continent.
- In late 2023, GIG with Anna Lowe from Manufacturing Change, the developer of the OCBM, established a mentoring programme for makerspaces to enhance their use of the catalogue. There were 35 applications from makerspaces for just three mentoring opportunities, highlighting the demand. The selected mentee spaces were Garoua in Cameroon, iZone Hub in Zimbabwe, and Habitat Augsburg in Germany.
 - In 2024, the IMA project received an additional grant, enabling ongoing collaboration between IMA and mAkE on the OCBM. This new grant will expand the mentoring programme, allowing makerspaces from four IMA countries (Ghana, Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa) to apply for mentoring support.
- GIG, ZSI and IAAC have secured further funding to support makers, particularly in Europe, with a new joint Horizon project, make-a-theK, set to launch in February 2025, supporting makerspaces and public libraries.. Drawing inspiration from the collaborative ethos and innovative objectives of the mAkE project, this initiative stands out as a further follow-up sustainability activity. It serves as a tangible outcome of the project while bringing a unique approach connecting a well-integrated ecosystem of libraries, craftworkers and maker spaces, open-source hardware innovation, and community-driven initiatives to deliver sustainable, scalable solutions that address pressing global challenges.
- There are numerous initiatives and activities for the international roll-out of mAkE results, especially to Latin American makerspaces, with goals e.g. including creating further Maker-in-Residency programmes, translating the OCBM to Spanish and Portuguese and advancing the coverage of the Map of Machinery as part of the Social Innovation Atlas. In time of submitting this report such funding proposals have not been successful yet.

Afrilabs Makerspace Track

To establish makerspaces as important aspects of DIHs in African and international DIH communities, the collaboration with the Afrilabs network was deepened and mAkE together

³¹ <https://localeconomies.org/blueprints>

³² <https://www.internetofproduction.org/innovative-manufacturing-awards>.

³³ <https://www.risa-fund.org/>

with IMA initiated the Afrilabs [Makerspace Track](#)³⁴ organised by Andrew Lamb of IOPA (UK), Fadia Elgharib of GIG (Egypt) and Tochukwu Chukwueke of the Clintonel Innovation Centre (Nigeria), which sought to share the work of the mAKE project and the impacts of makerspaces across Africa and beyond at the Afrilabs Annual Gathering³⁵ in Cape Town. This inaugural track recorded the highest attendance at the gathering, with over one hundred participants to the session. "For many, it wasn't just about learning but about imagining new possible futures for Africa and taking advantage of what the mAKE project had to offer," said co-organiser Joseph Agyina of IOPA (Ghana).

Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering

As part of mAKE legacy, the Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering was held in Cape Town, South Africa. This event brought together a diverse group of stakeholders, including makers, foundations, and government officials, to discuss strategies for advancing the growth and sustainability of makerspaces in Africa and Europe. The gathering was a crucial platform for fostering dialogue on supporting makerspaces to enhance local manufacturing, education, and community resilience. Participants had the unique opportunity to collaborate on innovative projects, exchange knowledge, and engage directly with representatives of foundations and donors to explore potential funding opportunities.

Figure 6. Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering, held in Cape Town, South Africa, in November 2024

Recognising the importance of an organised community, the event led to establishing a new member organisation for African makerspaces, aptly named **Africa Makerspaces**. This

³⁴ Press release reporting from the event:

<https://afrilabsgathering.com/afrilabs-annual-gathering-2024-spotlight-on-seven-dynamic-tracks-shaping-africas-innovation-landscape/>

³⁵ Event announcement:

<https://www.afrilabs.com/afrilabs-annual-gathering-2024-uniting-innovation-in-the-heart-of-cape-town/>

organisation, formed during the gathering, aims to include member makerspaces as active participants in decision-making processes that affect them. It is also designed to provide the necessary support for community growth and development.

A pivotal component of this initiative is creating a dedicated website for the new entity. The website will serve as a hub to showcase the impactful work of African makerspaces, provide resources, and advocate for the makerspace ecosystem. These efforts are directly aligned with the mAKE project's overarching vision of uniting makers on a shared platform where opportunities are readily accessible, collaboration thrives, and the impact of makerspaces continues to grow across both continents and beyond.

As part of the mAKE legacy, the new entity aims to adopt the mAKE design and eventually include mAKE materials to the website for continuity and growth of the achievement of the mAKE project.

The mAKE steering committee and secretariat

In 2025, a secretariat will be established in Cape Town, South Africa, where the final consortium meeting for 2024 took place. By enhancing the collaborations with the African network RLabs³⁶, based in Cape Town, the secretariat aims to cultivate a supportive local environment that facilitates the effective management of ongoing marketing and promotional activities aligned with the project's objectives and outcomes. We will appoint a local outreach champion and a marketing assistant with expertise in the maker movement to actively promote initiatives and goals at speaking engagements alongside fundraising efforts led by a voluntary steering committee from the consortium. This committee will comprise the following representatives:

- Ms. Geraldine de Bastion and Ms. Kirstin Wiedow, GIG
- Mr. Andrew Lamb, IOPA
- Ms. Anna Lowe, Manufacturing Change
- Ms. Kate Armstrong and Ms. Freda Yamorti Gbande, Fab City Foundation
- Ms. Fabienne Kirchhof, GreenTec Capital
- Mr. Guillem Camprodon and Ms. Jessica Guy, Fab Lab Barcelona | IAAC
- Mr. Joseph Agyina, Africa Makerspaces
- Dr. Thomas Hervé Mboa Nkoudou, APSOHA and AHIOSH
- Dr. Chris Armstrong, UCT-Open AIR
- Dr. Barbara Kieslinger, ZSI

Roles and responsibilities will include:

- Engaging with makerspaces across Africa to raise awareness of distributed manufacturing, mAKE outputs, and encourage consortium participation.

³⁶ <https://rlabs.org/>

- Mapping and participating in relevant policy processes related to distributed manufacturing continentally and globally.
- Maintaining ongoing communication through various channels.
- Fundraising for distributed manufacturing initiatives within Africa and internationally while promoting mAKE outputs and makerspaces.
- Coordinating educational activities and training sessions, updating resources as needed.
- Suggestion: Search for ways to expand mAKE further than Africa and Europe, reaching other continents and ecosystems of makerspaces.

Additional Responsibilities:

- Establishing connections with European and related global communities and networks.
- Strengthening relationships within the Vulca maker network.
- Connecting with Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Europe.
- Advancing the Distributed Design community.

The steering committee will play a crucial role in ensuring the successful attainment of the secretariat's goals, providing strategic direction and support for various initiatives. Regular meetings will be arranged to evaluate progress, address challenges, and explore new collaboration opportunities. To enhance the consortium's impact, we will utilise digital platforms to continue building repositories and share success stories, best practices, and innovative ideas emerging from the maker community following the integration of resources across the consortium. This strategy will raise awareness and inspire more individuals to engage in distributed manufacturing and the maker movement.

Additionally, a dedicated outreach will focus on cultivating relationships with key stakeholders, including government agencies, educational institutions, and private sector partners, to create synergies and boost the visibility of the consortium's initiatives. By fostering these partnerships, we aim to establish a sustainable ecosystem that encourages the growth of makerspaces and distributed manufacturing initiatives throughout Europe, Africa and beyond.

6. Conclusion

By focusing on community-supported Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and makerspaces, mAKE has emphasised the importance of innovative local production that meets specific local needs and conditions. This sustainability report illustrates the project's dedication to promoting innovation, ensuring financial sustainability, and fostering environmental stewardship.

Furthermore, it highlights how the project's deliverables—including the Venture Building Handbook, The Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT), the mAKE MOOC and the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)—create a flexible toolkit that empowers makerspaces to

customise their business strategies to align with their unique goals and community contexts. These resources aim not only to sustain the project's initiatives but also to enrich the ecosystem developed over the past 36 months. In addition to securing the project's future, these outcomes play a crucial role in supporting makerspaces and innovation hubs across Africa and Europe.

In conclusion, the consortium partners are dedicated to maintaining the project's legacy, guided by a steering committee and a formal secretariat that provides strategic oversight. The mAKE secretariat will offer vital resources and champion the ecosystem, aligning with the mAKE project's vision of connecting makers, fostering collaboration, and ensuring the lasting impact of the mAKE initiative. Regular meetings will be held to evaluate progress and encourage collaboration, utilising digital platforms to share best practices within the maker community.

Appendix A – Secretariat Budget

Item	Monthly (Euro)	Annually (Euro)
office (71sqm)	400	4.800
20-40% Time of Secretariat 'lead' (e.g. 1.5 days per/week)	1.680	20.160
Intern Fee	300	3.600
2 events e.g. Afrilabs/AMG and GIG Gathering re:publica (legacy)	n/a	5.000
	TOTAL	33.560

Appendix B – Insights from Sustainability Strategies within the ICT-58 Family

To gain insights into implemented sustainability strategies, GIG was able to interview representatives of three fellow EU Horizon 2020 programmes funded under the same call as mAKE, namely the ICT-58 family of projects³⁷. The ICT-58 family comprises mAKE, DIGILOGIC³⁸, HUBiquitous³⁹, AfriConEU⁴⁰, ENRICH in Africa⁴¹ and AEDIBINET⁴².

ENRICH in Africa

The ENRICH in Africa project was designed to connect and support innovation ecosystems in Europe and Africa. Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, it aimed to bring together key stakeholders from both regions to strengthen their innovation capabilities. The project focused on providing support services, facilitating collaboration, and integrating incubators and accelerators into a holistic EU-Africa innovation ecosystem. It began in 2021 and concluded in 2024 with activities structured in three phases: developing and piloting impactful initiatives, launching services to a broader community, and establishing the ENRICH in Africa Centre as a sustainable outcome.

As the primary sustainability approach, the ENRICH in Africa Centre was established during the project's runtime and continued operating independently after its completion in June 2024. Zandile Ntuli, the Centre's Manager, shared key learnings on the project's sustainability execution and how the monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) framework was adapted to review the processes. Reflecting on the project's flow and the development and implementation of the sustainability strategy, she emphasised, "The best practice and lesson learned would be to share". She highlighted four "share" elements illustrated in Figure 1. *ENRICH in Africa Sustainability Insights* below.

First, the sustainability solution must provide added value, ensuring it can be adopted by the market and remain self-sufficient after the project ends. To obtain this capacity to share the findings of the project, one of the most critical factors is to "get the key people", entailing not merely that they are the means to accomplish sustainability but also "the solution of the sustainability" themselves because most of them were in the project and carry the legacies of the project.

Second, creating a data repository is pivotal for sustaining the data and network created by the project. More importantly, this repository should be accessible and shareable. The trick of maintaining a data repository, she thought, was to have a sustainable partner who would

³⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/ict-58-2020>

³⁸ <https://digilogic.africa/>

³⁹ <https://hubiquitous.eu/>

⁴⁰ <https://africoneu.eu/>

⁴¹ <https://enrich-in-africa-project.eu/>

⁴² <https://aedibnet.eu/>

take care of it and the intellectual property (IP). ENRICH in Africa project reviewed past initiatives and saw who they could partner with to take care of the data repository.

Third, identifying a leading actor to share project results is crucial. Ntuli recommended selecting one makerspace or hub from the project community to act as the sustainable “vehicle”. The twofold entity exemplifies: on one hand, the self-sustainable business model; on the other hand, it is geared to act as the custodian of the project's findings that people will refer to within the community or in the broader world.

Finally, an ecosystem that is an enabler of sharing the project’s legacy should be built up and developed. Zandile Ntuli shared two specific examples. Creating a forum where all the partners own the information created in the project and commit to sustaining the community is a way to practice a joint sustainability partnership. In addition, mapping the community connected through the project in an open-source manner can also help sustain the vibrancy and navigate for future possibilities and encounters.

Figure 7. ENRICH in Africa Sustainability Insights

As one of the outcomes of the sustainability activities, the project SEADE (Strengthening the Europe–Africa Digital Ecosystem Through Increased R&I Cooperation) funded under the EU’s Horizon Europe programme, builds on the legacy of ENRICH in Africa and extends it by integrating researchers into the network. These dynamics, according to Ntuli, “gives more push for the sustainability of the Centre” for securing additional resources. As a result of its strategic sustainability efforts, the ENRICH in Africa Centre has successfully achieved two key objectives: one is “to ensure that the people worked in the Center are hired”, and the other one is to maintain a space for people “to exercise the business model” developed in the project, Ntuli said.

DIGILOGIC

DIGILOGIC aims to boost the cooperation and strategic partnership between European and African Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) by developing the Pan EU–Africa DIGILOGIC Hub – the EU–AU decentralised DIH dedicated to smart logistics. DIGILOGIC aims to foster the creation of a community of stakeholders to stimulate and shape the adoption of emerging technologies (e.g. cloud computing, big data, machine learning, blockchain, intelligent objects) for smart logistics solutions, through the deployment of a dynamic and impactful knowledge transfer and implementation programme. The project kicked off in January 2021 and ended in December 2023.

An interview with Charlotte Edzard⁴³, the Lead Project Manager of the H2020-funded project DIGILOGIC, was conducted in November 2024. As illustrated in the **Figure. DIGILOGIC Sustainability Insights** below, she shared three main approaches to the sustainability strategies of the project. First and foremost, the Smart Steps⁴⁴ project serves as DIGILOGIC’s ongoing community platform. It not only inherits the community of the African logistics sector built up during the runtime of DIGILOGIC but also interlinks with the e-learning component in DIGILOGIC and shares the learner pool of DIGILOGIC consisting of its potential users. Edzard stated: “It works out the best among all the approaches because it is a self-sustainable and alive system in which users are active and where the value of DIGILOGIC remains.”

The second asset is the Logistics Trend Radar⁴⁵, which elaborates on the trend of the logistics industry in Africa by attaining insights from the network of major logistics companies and research institutes. A long-term road map was created in the societal, technological, and biological dimensions. The last main asset of DIGILOGIC is the Policy Recommendation Paper, the pillar of collaboration between digital innovation hubs. Edzard further shared that, “This document was not initially planned, but it organically formed in the processes of collaborations with the ICT–58 project family⁴⁶ projects including mAKE.”

⁴³ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/charlotte-edzard/>

⁴⁴ <https://smartstep-community.com/en/>

⁴⁵ https://digilogic.africa/trend_radar/

⁴⁶ [EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#)

Figure 8. DIGILOGIC Sustainability Insights

Revisiting the flow of sustainability strategy developments, the interview culminated in three reflections to share with the mAKE project team, namely:

- It's better to speak with the target user groups of the assets when developing the strategies for understanding their needs, easier imaging the scenarios of using it and whether the asset should be free or fee-charge,
- Investing time and effort in discussing with the project partners is always worthwhile. This will ensure a collective decision-making process and that something impactful will happen when the project closes.
- More time should be invested in figuring out who takes the lead on each asset so that the implementations can work more smoothly after the project ends and meet the expectations of how the assets have been designed.

HUBiquitous

HUBiquitous⁴⁷ aimed to create a joint Africa-Europe Startup & Innovation Ecosystem for collaborations and partnerships. The project had the ambition to increase the technology level and capacity building of 30 local Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)/Tech Hubs in 5 African countries. The project has ended and been reviewed in October 2024.

Dr. Abdur Rahim Biswas, the Technical Manager of HUBiquitous, took the time to share his inspiration for sustaining the legacies of the project. Sustainability, as emphasised by him, was an integral part of the project from its inception. "To get sustainability is to be well

⁴⁷ <https://hubiquitous.eu/>

thought of at the beginning of the project and to understand which result we want to sustain, who will be the owner of the result and then the maintenance cost and what is the value of the result.”

One of the main tools developed by the project was the Wazilab⁴⁸ Platform, designed to connect various hubs and foster learning and skill development. This platform has demonstrated significant success, boasting approximately 1,500 registered users, with new users joining daily even after the project's conclusion. This continued engagement is a strong indicator of sustainability. Another major legacy of the project is the creation of an active community, which continues to expand and collaborate. Various curricula and learning materials were also developed and are being further enhanced, ensuring long-term educational impact. Despite its successes, the project encountered challenges in sustaining some of its impacts. The MeetHub platform, for example, lacked a concrete exploitation plan, which led to difficulties in maintaining its long-term value.

In the interview with mAkE, Biswas offered several key recommendations for future EU projects and similar initiatives:

- **Define Sustainability Goals Early:** Clearly identify which results should be sustained and establish ownership from the beginning.
- **Ensure Commitment from Stakeholders:** A defined entity or consortium members must take responsibility for maintaining and utilising project outcomes.
- **Maintain Focus on Sustainability During Execution:** Regularly revisit sustainability plans to ensure alignment with project goals.
- **Leverage Project Outcomes for New Funding:** Strong results can be used to secure additional funding for continued development and integration into new projects.

HUBiquitous demonstrates that well-planned sustainability leads to lasting impact. By prioritising ownership, resource allocation, and long-term vision, projects can create legacies that extend beyond their completion. Sustainability is not an afterthought—it must be embedded from day one, Biswas stressed repeatedly.

⁴⁸ <https://lab.waziup.io/>

Appendix C – Right to Repair Policy Directive

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

Right to Repair Policy Directive

An instrument for green and digital transformation

Author:
Geraldine de Bastion

Editors:
Samuel Boadu Duah, Freda Yamorti Obande, Barbara Kieslinger and Joseph Agyina

gig GLOBAL INNOVATION GATHERING

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makeafricaeu.org

Executive summary

The Right to Repair is an instrument for green and digital transformation. It can help reduce waste and resource use, democratise access to technology, as well as promote economic and social justice by empowering citizens and upholding consumer rights. The EU can strengthen the Right to Repair globally by:

- **Mandating Modular and Open Design:** Enforce modular and open design standards for digital hardware to allow easy replacement of components, requiring access to repair manuals and spare parts while balancing intellectual property rights.
- **Encouraging Producer Responsibility:** Require manufacturers to design products with longevity and reparability in mind, promoting sustainable practices such as cradle-to-cradle production and accountability for full product life cycles, including end-of-life recycling.
- **Preventing Software-Induced Obsolescence:** Regulate software updates to ensure they do not shorten hardware lifespans, preventing unnecessary e-waste by maintaining device functionality.
- **Building Open Repair Ecosystems:** Develop open-access repair databases and repositories for sharing repair knowledge, methods, and resources, fostering a culture of community-led repair and supporting a global repair network.

Distributed manufacturing empowers consumers and local repair facilities by enabling the production of parts closer to where they are needed, thus minimising transportation emissions and supporting local economies. The Right to Repair and distributed manufacturing both support local economic resilience, reduce e-waste, and provide consumers with greater autonomy. Together, they can be part of a systemic approach for a just and inclusive digital and green transition.

Photo credits: Peter Nicholls | the Times

Appendix D – Policy Brief: Improving Visa Policies for African Innovators in International Cooperation Projects

(*design to be completed in February 2025)

Intransparent and unfair visa policies are undermining international cooperation efforts by restricting access to key opportunities, particularly for African innovators. These policies disproportionately affect women, especially young women, creating systemic barriers to participation and collaboration.

Visa Policy Challenges in Europe-Africa Cooperation

The Global Innovation Gathering e.V. (GIG) has a decade of experience hosting members from around the world at the Berlin-based event, re:publica. Every year, some speakers face rejected visa applications without proper explanation, particularly young women, while others encounter severe difficulties throughout the visa application process. Over the past three years, GIG was one of X consortium members implementing the Horizon 2020-funded project mAkE, a program designed to foster collaboration and innovation between African and European makers. However, the same obstacles repeatedly emerged during the project's lifespan, with participants struggling to obtain visas to attend key events and co-creation programs.

These challenges were not just individual setbacks. They directly hindered the project's outcomes, preventing critical collaboration opportunities and undermining the objectives of EU-funded development programs. This policy brief is aimed at EU policymakers and encourages them to address the contradiction between the EU's support for cross-continental cooperation and the restrictive visa practices of its member states.

Lessons Learned from the mAkE Project: The Impact of Visa Obstacles on Cooperation

The mAkE project aimed to establish sustainable economic relations between makerspaces engaged in distributed manufacturing and innovation. Its activities included co-creation workshops, venture-building programs, and events where African and European makers could network, showcase their work, and develop partnerships. One of the key activities was the Maker-in-Residency (MiR) Program, designed to create synergies by bringing together innovators working on hardware

solutions and supporting them in advancing their projects to market readiness. However, throughout the project, visa challenges consistently obstructed participation. These challenges can be grouped into three key areas:

Limited Access to Visa Appointments and Long Wait Times: In many countries, applicants experienced extreme difficulty securing visa appointments within a reasonable timeframe. Appointments for Schengen visas were often controlled by private third-party entities that charged fees, exacerbating the financial burden for applicants. Some applicants had to wait months, missing short- and mid-term opportunities like conferences and fundraising events, which typically require flexible planning. For example, a maker from Cameroon missed three major events over the course of the project due to the inability to secure timely appointments or have their visas issued on time, despite submitting complete documentation.

Prolonged Processing Times: Even when applicants secured appointments and submitted their applications months before the planned travel dates, processing times were often excessively long. This caused significant delays in project activities and missed opportunities for cross-border collaboration. For instance, a Nigerian maker was unable to join the MiR program because their visa approval process extended beyond the program's start date, despite their early application and the submission of all required materials. The prolonged process undermined the project's ability to bring together diverse perspectives and expertise.

Lack of Transparency and Unexplained Rejections: Applicants frequently faced visa rejections without adequate justification or detailed explanations. Many of these rejections occurred even when applicants provided the necessary documentation and the project staff directly communicated with embassies to verify the purpose of travel. Alarming, women applicants seemed to be disproportionately affected by visa denials. Efforts to appeal these decisions were often unsuccessful, as applicants and project team members were unable to obtain responses from embassies or receive guidance through official channels. This lack of transparency not only created frustration but also resulted in significant financial losses and missed opportunities.

The consequences of these visa challenges have been substantial: Both applicants and the project incurred significant costs related to securing appointments, navigating lengthy application processes, and addressing rejected applications. The time spent on these issues diverted attention from core project objectives. Further, many African makers were unable to attend key events and engage in collaborative activities that were essential to building sustainable economic and creative partnerships. The delays caused by visa-related obstacles hindered the timely implementation of the project, reducing its overall effectiveness and the long-term development benefits it aimed to deliver. By limiting access to critical collaboration

opportunities, restrictive visa policies directly counteract the EU's goals of fostering international cooperation and sustainable development.

Policy Recommendations

To address these issues and enable future cooperation projects to thrive, we recommend the following policy improvements:

Implement Transparent Systems for Visa Appointment Distribution:

Visa appointment systems should be transparent and directly managed by embassies or consulates, without the involvement of third-party entities charging additional fees. Applicants should have equal access to appointments through a fair and publicly accessible system.

Ensure Clear and Digital Visa Application Processes:

Visa application procedures should be streamlined and digitized, allowing applicants to submit all necessary documentation online. The system should include application tracking features so applicants can monitor the status of their applications and plan accordingly.

Provide Transparency Regarding Rejected Applications:

Visa denials should be accompanied by explanations specifying the reasons for rejection and any missing documentation or errors. This would enable applicants to address issues in future applications and improve the overall trust in the system.

Address Gender Disparities in Visa Processing:

Given the disproportionate rejection rates among women, EU member states should conduct a gender-based review of visa policies and processing practices. This aligns with the principles of feminist foreign policy, which seek to address systemic gender inequities and promote inclusion.

Incorporate Feminist Foreign Policy Values:

Visa policies should reflect the EU's commitment to feminist foreign policy by promoting inclusivity, transparency, and fairness in decision-making. Embassies should receive training on these values and be held accountable for ensuring that visa applicants are treated equitably.

Facilitate Visa Support for EU-Funded Programs:

A special streamlined visa pathway should be established for participants in EU-funded programs, recognizing the strategic importance of their participation. This could involve pre-approved lists or expedited processing for applicants directly involved in development cooperation projects.

By addressing these challenges, EU policymakers can ensure that visa policies no longer hinder international cooperation but instead act as enablers of global innovation and development partnerships.

Survey:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSc-DI5n9XPisduYCYwLU6HRjraheJP3Cng0v7rRsVdxojhDqQ/viewform?usp=dialog>

